

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TRENDS IN EMERGING RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TRENDS IN EMERGING RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

Volume 3; Issue 5; 2025; Page No. 57-61

Received: 01-06-2025
Accepted: 06-07-2025
Published: 07-09-2025

A study to assess the effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on knowledge regarding home care of psychotic patients among their primary care givers in selected hospital at Bilaspur Chhattisgarh

¹Roshani Mahant, ²Vartika Gouraha and ³Ajeeta Panna

¹M.Sc., Department of Mental Health Nursing, Government College of Nursing, Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh, India

²Associate Professor and HOD, Department of Mental Health Nursing, Government College of Nursing, Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh, India

³Demonstrator, Department of Mental Health Nursing, Government College of Nursing, Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh, India

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17212312>

Corresponding Author: Roshani Mahant

Abstract

Psychotic condition characterized by a disturbance in thinking, emotions, volitions and faculties in the presence of clear consciousness, which usually leads to social withdrawal. Schizophrenia is the most common of all psychiatric disorders and is prevalent in all cultures across the world. Innovative educational programs can make a valuable contribution. Videotapes can be effective teaching tools for patients and caregivers by facilitating knowledge acquisition, reducing anxiety, improving coping skills, and enhancing self-care Behaviors and reducing burden. They are valuable resources for assistance in educating patients and caregivers in today's changing health care environment. They incorporate visual and auditory information into a teaching modality that is often easy for individuals to understand and retain.

Keywords: Video assisted teaching programme, knowledge, home care, psychotic patients, primary caregivers

Introduction

Psychosis is a condition characterized by a loss of contact with reality, which may include symptoms such as hallucinations (seeing or hearing things that are not present) and delusions (strongly held false beliefs). It can occur due to various underlying medical conditions, substance use, or as a symptom of a psychotic disorder.

Signs of Early or First-Episode Psychosis, There is some overlap with early warning signs as it is difficult to pinpoint exactly when the first episode of psychosis begins. These signs include: Sensory experiences (hearing, seeing, tasting, and less commonly, feeling or smelling things) that are not real, Social withdrawal/withdrawing from family or friends, Strong, inappropriate emotions, or not feeling anything at all, Sudden decline in self-care, Strong, persistent, unusual thoughts or beliefs that are false, and do not change

regardless of evidence to the contrary, Difficulty concentrating or thinking clearly.

Between 50 and 80 percent of schizophrenics live with family members and the patient becomes the priority in the family for illness, as well as preventing relapse, keeping their loved one healthy and worries about their financial expenses of hospital or medication.

The caregivers of Psychosis provide considerable support to their ill relatives for this reason the caregivers need to have provision of information to the primary caregivers linked to better outcomes. The information required for caregivers are on the illness, its symptoms, different treatment options, medications and their therapeutic uses and their adverse side effects, signs of relapse, availability of community services and supports, how to access benefits and entitlements, and how to handle crises or bizarre and troubling behaviours.

In India, families represent the key resource persons in the care of patients with Psychosis. Families are assigned the role of primary care takers for two reasons. First, there is paucity of trained professionals to execute psychosocial interventions and second, most Indian families would like to be meaningfully involved in all aspects of care of their ill relative.

Problem Statement

“A study to assess the effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on knowledge regarding home care of psychotic patients among their primary care givers in selected hospital at Bilaspur Chhattisgarh.”

Objectives of the study

1. To assess the pre-test and post-test level of knowledge regarding home care of psychotic patient among their primary caregivers.
2. To evaluate the effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on knowledge regarding home care of psychotic patients among their primary care givers.
3. To find out the association of pre-test knowledge score of primary care givers with their selected socio-demographic variables.

Hypothesis

- H₁:** There will be significant difference between pre-test and post- test level of knowledge score regarding home care of psychotic patients among their primary care givers.
- H₂:** There will be significant association between pre-test knowledge score regarding home care of psychotic patient among their primary care givers with selected socio demographic variables.

Operational definition

Assess: In the study it refers to evaluate the knowledge on home care of psychosis patients among their primary care givers.

Effectiveness: In this study, it refer to the benefit of video assisted teaching programme to bring about change in knowledge of primary care givers on home care of psychosis patient of gaining in knowledge score.

Video Assisted Teaching Programme: It refers to systematically organised audio & visual information to teach primary caregivers regarding home care of Psychotic patients to improve knowledge, to develop their skill and to decrease caregiver burden.

Knowledge: In the present study, knowledge is correct response to the knowledge in the structured closed ended questionnaire regarding home care of psychosis patients

Home care: According to the present study, home care refers to the care which can be given to the Psychosis patients at home by primary caregivers. It includes administration of medication, diet for psychosis, handling expressed emotions, Safety precautions, and preventive measures of relapse, management of delusion and hallucination, and personal hygiene.

Psychotic patients: Refers to the patients who are diagnosed as psychosis as per the criteria of DSM IV/ICD 10 classification and being treated for psychosis as inpatient or outpatient in selected hospitals at Bilaspur Chhattisgarh.

Primary caregivers: In the present study, primary caregivers refers to the family members of a patient diagnosed as psychosis, residing with the patient in the selected hospital and involved in regular care of the psychotic patient including follow-up care and hospital visits.

Conceptual framework

A conceptual framework deals with the abstraction, which are assembled together. This study is intended to assess the effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on knowledge regarding home care of psychotic patients among their primary care givers in selected hospital at Bilaspur (C.G.).

The conceptual framework of the present study was modified by the investigator based on Imogene King's goal attainment model. The concepts are interrelated in every nursing situation. These are define as concept in the conceptual framework.

Research Methodology

Quantitative approach was used in this study, to assess the effectiveness of Video Assisted Teaching Programme on knowledge regarding home care of psychotic patients in selected hospital, Bilaspur Chhattisgarh. The research design is selected for the present study was pre experimental one group pre-test and post- test design. The sample size was 60 Primary care givers of psychotic patients, non-probability purposive sampling technique was used for this study. Data was collected using a validated & reliable tools developed such as socio-demographic variables, knowledge questionnaire regarding home care of psychotic patients. Video assisted teaching programme was implemented to the primary care givers & post test was done on 7th day of intervention. Data collection was analyzed by an paired ‘Z’ test. The data was analysed by micro-excel sheet.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Organization of Data for Analysis

The analysis of data is organized and presented under the following broad headings.

Section I: Distribution of subjects according to socio demographic variables in frequency & percentage

Section II: (A) Assessment of pre-test – post-test knowledge score regarding home care of psychotic patients through mean, mean percentage, mean difference, standard deviation.

(B) Criteria wise analysis of pre - test and post - test level of knowledge score by frequency and percentage.

Section III: Evaluation of data related to effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on knowledge regarding home care of psychotic patients using “Z – test”.

Section IV: Association between selected socio

demographic variables with pre-test knowledge of primary care givers regarding home care of psychotic patients, using – “chi Squire test”.

Section I

Distribution of subjects according to socio demographic variables in frequency & percentage

The majority of primary care givers age in years are 45% (27) primary care givers belong to age group of 18-27years, were 30% (18) belong to age 38-47 years, 25% (15) belong to age group of 28-37 years, and none of the primary care givers were in the age group of 48-60 years.

The majority of genders are 81.66% (49) are male and 18.88% (11) are female.

The educational status majority of primary care givers were 32% (19) educated up to middle school education, 25% (15) up to primary school education, 25% (15) were graduate, and 18% (11) up to higher school education.

The majority of occupation are 50% (30) of primary care givers were House wife, 17% (10) of primary care givers had private job, 15% (09) of primary care givers had other works, 10% (06) of primary care givers were self-business and 8% (05) of primary care givers had Govt.job.

The majority of area of residence are 67% (40) of primary care givers belong to rural areas and 33% (20) belong to urban areas.

The majority of types of family are 50% (30) of primary

care givers belong to the Joint Family, 33% (20) belong to Nuclear family and 17% (10) primary care givers belong to the extended family.

The majority of relationship of caregivers are 40% (24) primary care providers were fathers, 33% (20) were mothers, 13% (08) were brothers, 10% (06) were others, and 3% (02) were sisters.

The majority of source of previous knowledge of primary care givers regarding home care of psychotic patients were relatives 67% (40), health workers sources of information were 17% (10), television sources of information were 10% (06), and newspaper sources of information were 7% (04).

Section II

First objective of the study was to assess the pre-test and post-test level of knowledge regarding home care of psychotic patient among their primary caregivers.

(A) Assessment of pre test - post test knowledge score regarding home care of psychotic patients through total mean, mean score percentage, mean difference, standard deviation.

The finding revealed that the total knowledge score was 519 out of 1800 that is mean 8.65, mean score percentage 28.83% and standard deviation 3.98 in pre-test and in post-test the knowledge score was 1109 out of 1800 that is means 18.4, mean score percentage 61.61% and standard deviation 4.26 Mean difference of pre test & post test is 32.78.

(B) Criteria wise analysis of pre-test and post-test level of knowledge score by frequency and percentage.

The finding revealed that knowledge score between pre test and post test where, in pre-test majority of subjects 80% (48) have poor knowledge, 20% (28) have average

knowledge and 0% (0) have good knowledge. In post-test majority of subjects 83.33% (50) have good knowledge, 16.66% (10) have average knowledge and none of them have poor knowledge regarding home care of psychotic patients.

Section III

Second objective was to evaluate the effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on knowledge regarding home care of psychotic patients among their primary care givers.

Evaluation of data related to effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on knowledge regarding home care of psychotic patients using “z – test”.

Finding revealed that there was an effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme, significance difference between pre-test & post-test on knowledge regarding home care of psychotic patients among their primary care givers as calculated value of Z-test is 13.07 is greater than table value 2.00 at 0.05 level of significance.

So H₁ hypothesis is accepted with regard to knowledge there is significant increased post – test knowledge score regarding home care of psychotic patients among their primary care givers in selected hospital Bilaspur (C.G).

Section IV

Third objective was to find out the association of pre-test knowledge score of primary care givers with their selected socio-demographic variables.

Association between selected socio demographic variables with pre test knowledge score of primary care givers regarding home care of psychotic patients, using – “chi square test”.

The analysis reveals statistically that socio demographic variable age, gender, educational status, occupational status, residence of primary care givers, types of family, relationship of primary care givers, had no significant association with the pre-test level of knowledge and source of previous knowledge of primary care givers had significant association with the pre-test level of knowledge of primary care givers of psychotic patients, at the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the H₂ was accepted.

Summary

This chapter has dealt with the discussion of major finding of the study under different sections such as distribution of subject according to socio demographic variables using frequency and percentage, assessment of pre test - post test

knowledge score regarding home care of psychotic patients through mean, mean percentage, mean difference, standard deviation, Evaluation of the effectiveness of video assisted teaching programme on knowledge regarding home care of psychotic patients among their primary care givers in selected hospital at Bilaspur (C.G) and Chi square analysis carried out to find out the association between selected socio demographic variables with pre-test knowledge of primary care givers regarding home care of psychotic patient.

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